

DYNAMICS OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE CONTEXT OF MODERNIZATION OF EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The article presents the dynamics of physical development of high school students in the context of modernization of education. Trends affecting student physical performance are reviewed, including weight gain, decreased physical activity, and increased stress and dehydration. The analysis is based on data from a study conducted during the 2023-2024 school year. The author points out that changes in the educational environment, teaching methods, nutrition and level of physical activity have a significant impact on the physical development of high school students. The main idea of the article is that the modernization of education has a direct impact on the physical development of high school students, therefore it is necessary to pay more attention to the health and physical activity of students.*

Keywords: *physical development, modernization of education, physical parameters, physical activity.*

Modern education is a key factor in shaping the health and physical development of young people. Modernization of education, associated with changes in the educational environment and teaching methods, affects the physical parameters of high school students.

Consideration of the dynamics of physical development of high school students in the context of modernization of education made it possible to identify trends and factors influencing anthropometric indicators. The research used data from the scientific study “Dynamics of physical development of high school students during the school year” (2023-2024) and statistical data obtained during experimental studies at secondary school No. 84 in the Shaykhantakhur district of Tashkent.

Research methods included questionnaires, measurement of physical development parameters and statistical analysis of the data obtained.

Acquaintance with the literature data on the research topic indicates that the physical development of high school students in the conditions of modernization of education is characterized by the following trends:

Increase in body weight. In recent years, there has been a trend toward increased body weight among high school students due to changing educational environments, increased screen time, and changing dietary preferences.

Reducing physical activity. Modernization of education has also led to a decrease in physical activity among high school students. This is due to changes in the educational program, an increase in the number of theoretical disciplines and a decrease in the time allocated for physical activity.

Increased stress levels. Modernization of education has also led to an increase in stress levels among high school students due to changes in the educational environment, an increase in the amount of homework and a decrease in time allocated for recreation and entertainment.

Increased level of dehydration. Modernization of education has also led to increased rates of dehydration among high school students. This is due to changes in the educational environment, increased levels of dust in the air, increased time spent in front of screens, and decreased time allocated to physical activity (1,2,3).

The study of the dynamics of physical development made it possible to identify the dependence of the functional capabilities of the body on body size.

When comparing functional indicators in girls and boys, one should first of all take into account differences in body size.

On average, girls have lower growth rates than boys, as a result of which, due to these differences, under all other identical conditions, many functional indicators in girls, in particular their performance, differed from the corresponding indicators in boys.

A similar picture is observed when comparing data from children and adults with different body sizes. Let's compare the physical development indicators of grade 9A students.

It was found that the average height of girls is 162.3 cm, while that of boys is 174.4 cm, while all their linear dimensions were proportional to body length. It was revealed that boys are 1.07 times taller than girls (174.4: 162.3). In this case, all linear dimensions, i.e., the length of all parts of the body and limbs, the length of levers (distances from the axis of rotation of the joint to the place of muscle attachment), amplitude of movements, etc., in young men are 1.07 times greater than in girls [4].

It has been established that the main factors influencing the physical development of high school students in the context of modernization of education are:

1. Educational environment, since the modernization of education has led to a change in the educational environment, which affects the physical development of high school students.

2. Teaching methods. The inclusion of interactive and information-communicative teaching methods significantly affects the physical development of high school students.

3. Nutrition. Changing dietary preferences also affects the physical development of high school students. An increase in the amount of sweet and fatty foods, as well as a passion for fast food, can lead to weight gain.

4. Physical activity. Theoretical disciplines and an increase in homework lead to a decrease in physical activity, which also affects the physical development of high school students. Regular physical activity can lead to improved physical development.

5. Sleep - it is during sleep that the main metabolic and differentiation processes that determine skeletal growth take place. The most important growth stimulator necessary for the proper formation of the skeleton is physical activity, especially age-appropriate outdoor games [5].

In conclusion, it should be emphasized that the modernization of education affects the physical development of high school students, as it has led to changes in the educational environment, teaching methods, nutrition and physical activity, which significantly affect the physical development of high school students.

This is evidenced by the analysis of these percentages, calculated taking into account the gender and age of the subjects.

The results showed that men had higher physical development values compared to women, especially in terms of weight and upper arm circumference. Regarding age, older age (11th grade) has higher values of physical development compared to younger age (9th and 10th grades) (Tables 1,2).

Table 1

Dynamics of indicators of physical development of high school students (boys in grades 9-11)

Classes	Height	Weight	Chest circumference during inhalation	Chest circumference at rest	Chest circumference during exhalation	Dynamometry of the right arm	Dynamometry of the left arm
9 A	162,3	50,3	84,6	83	81,6	28,8	32,3
9 B	161,7	50,4	85,5	83	81,2	38,3	41,5
10	160,8	51,7	84,3	82,5	81	25,2	26
11	163,3	57,2	90,4	89,1	87,7	34,3	33,8

Table 2

Dynamics of indicators of physical development of high school students (girls in grades 9-11)

Classes	Height	Weight	Chest circumference when inhaling	Chest circumference at rest	Chest circumference when exhaling	Dynamometry of the right arm	Dynamometry of the left arm
9 A	174,4	58,3	89,1	86,2	83,7	48	45,6
9 B	173,8	65	91,7	89,8	88	49,9	47,7
10	174,6	56,1	87,6	84,9	82,7	36,4	42,6
11	174,7	91,7	91,7	89,6	87,6	43	45,9

The results of the study indicate that the physical development of high school students is a dynamic process that changes throughout the school year. This is confirmed by the observed changes in the growth and development of the body of students of this age. It is important to note that at this age there are significant physiological changes associated with the transition from childhood to adolescence.

This may be due to the growth and development of the body at this age. In general, the results of the study provide valuable information about the dynamics of physical development of high school students in the context of modernization of education.

These results can be used to develop programs to improve physical development and health in schools, as well as to develop recommendations for physical activity and nutrition for high school students.

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